

NANOSTRUCTURED COMPOSITE MATERIALS FROM MICROFIBRILLATED CELLULOSE AND CARBON NANOTUBES

M. Salajkova^{1,2}, H. Sehaqui¹, Q. Zhou^{1,3}, L. A. Berglund¹

¹Department of Fibre and Polymer Technology, Royal Institute of Technology, SE-100 44 Stockholm, Sweden; ²Institute of Materials Chemistry, Brno University of Technology, 612 00 Brno, Czech Republic; ³School of Biotechnology, Royal Institute of Technology, AlbaNova University Centre, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden
qi@kth.se

SUMMARY

Thin composite films were prepared from the mixture of the aqueous suspension of microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The morphology, electrical conductivity, and mechanical properties of the composites were characterized. Good electrical properties were obtained when the MWCNTs content was higher than 2 wt%.

Keywords: Composite Materials, Cellulose nanofibers, Carbon nanotubes, Mechanical properties, Electrical conductivity

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose nanofibers refer to a class of nanoscale constituents prepared by microfibrillation from wood pulp, bacterial cellulose, and tunicate whiskers. Cellulose nanofibers have unique properties, such as small size, immense strength and stiffness, and the ability to form entangled network structure, a reactive surface that facilitates grafting chemical species to achieve different surface properties. Nanotechnology, which consists of manipulating materials and devices of 100 nm or less in at least one dimension, provides us an opportunity to create advanced materials with hierarchical structures^[1] and develop cellulose-based materials with higher strength,^[2] greater optical transparency,^[3] or enhanced electrical and magnetic performances.^[4]

Since their discovery, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted considerable interest in both academia and industry because of their extraordinary physical, chemical, and structural properties.^[5] In particular, fabrication of cellulose/CNTs composite sheets and their possible applications, *e.g.* light emitting diodes, high-strength cables and substrates, have been extensively reported.^[6-8]

In the present work, multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) were dispersed in water using a surfactant, and thin composite films were prepared from the mixture of the aqueous suspension of microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) and MWCNTs. The structure, electrical conductivity, and mechanical properties the composite films were characterized.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of the thin composite films

As-received MWCNTs (Thomas Swan, Elicarb®; purity 70–90 %, prepared by chemical vapour deposition, average outer diameter 10–12 nm with length in order of tens of microns) were dispersed in water with sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and high-shear mixing (Ultra Turrax T25 basic, IKA; 13000 rpm, 1 hour) followed by sonication with a rod-type sonicator for 4×2.5 min (Branson Sonifier 250, output 10, 70 % – pulsing 0.7 s on, 0.3 s off). MWCNTs suspension was then mixed with the aqueous suspension of MFC. Thin composite films with the MWCNTs content in the range of 0.1–5.0 wt% were prepared using vacuum filtration followed by drying under vacuum at 93 °C for 10 min in the sheet former (Rapid Kothen RK3A-KWT PTI).

Characterization

Surface resistivity (ρ_s) was measured using Keithly 6517B Electrometer/High Resistivity Meter together with a Keithly 8009 Resistivity Test Fixture. Tensile test was performed using Miniature Materials Tester (MiniMat2000) with a 200 N load cell. Rectangular samples with dimensions 5×30 mm were tested. The gap between the clamps was 10 mm and the loading rate was 1 mm/min. Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM; Hitachi S-4800) analysis was performed in order to investigate the morphology of the composite films. The samples were mounted onto a metal sample holder using colloidal graphite, and coated with carbon (Carbon coater Cressington 108 carbon/A; 3 s) and gold/palladium (Sputter coater Cressington 208 HR; 4 nm). Low accelerating voltage (0.7–1 kV), short working distance (2–3 mm) and the secondary electron detector were used.

Figure 1. FE-SEM micrograph of the MFC film.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 1, pure MFC film consists of cellulose nanofibres that are entangled with each other. The orientation seems to be mostly random-in-the-plane and the structure is in agreement with previously published data.^[2] The FE-SEM micrograph of the MFC/MWCNTs composite film with 5 wt% of MWCNTs is shown in Figure 2. MWCNTs were incorporated into cellulose nanofibres network, and evidence of the formation of continuous MWCNTs network was obtained by the surface resistivity analysis.

Figure 2. FE-SEM micrograph of the composite film with 5 wt% of MWCNTs.

Figure 3. Surface resistivity data for composite films containing MWCNTs.

The electrical conductivity of the composite is strongly dependent on the loading of CNTs. At low CNTs concentrations, the conductivity remains very close to the conductivity of the pure polymer matrix since CNTs are dispersed individually or in

small clusters in the matrix. When a critical filler volume fraction, the percolation threshold, is reached, the conductivity remarkably increases by many orders of magnitude. This is due to the formation of a conductive, three-dimensional network of the CNTs in the continuous polymer matrix.^[9] Figure 3 shows the surface resistivity versus the MWCNTs content for the MFC/MWCNTs composite films. When the MWCNTs content was lower than 0.5 wt%, the surface resistivities of the composite films were similar to that of the pure MFC. However, the surface resistivity of the composite films decreased significantly by 9 orders of magnitude when MWCNTs with a content higher than 2 wt% were added. Good electrical property was obtained with surface resistivities lower than $1.8 \times 10^5 \Omega/\text{sq}$, indicating that the MWCNTs were incorporated uniformly and densely into the microfibrillated cellulose network.

CONCLUSION

Composite materials from MFC and MWCNTs were successfully prepared. With the addition of 2 wt% of MWCNTs, the surface resistivity of the composite films decreased by 9 orders of magnitude compared to pure MFC film. Both cellulose nanofibres and carbon nanotubes are materials with promising potential in many different applications.^[5] Potential advantages of these materials lie in their flexibility, high strength, electrical conductivity, lightweight and transparency and they can be used for example in optoelectronic and as sensors and actuators.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank Mikael Segersäll for performing the surface resistivity measurements.

References

1. A. J. Svagan, M. Samir, L. A. Berglund, *Adv. Mater.* 2008, 20, 1263.
2. M. Henriksson, L. A. Berglund, P. Isaksson, T. Lindstrom, T. Nishino, *Biomacromolecules* 2008, 9, 1579.
3. H. Yano, J. Sugiyama, A. N. Nakagaito, M. Nogi, T. Matsuura, M. Hikita, K. Handa, *Adv. Mater.* 2005, 17, 153.
4. J. Shah, R. M. Brown, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 2005, 66, 352.
5. H.S. Kim *et al.*, *Biomacromolecules* 2009, 10, 82.
6. T. Oya, T. Ogino, *Carbon* 2008, 46, 169.
7. Z. Yan *et al.*, *Carbohydr. Res.* 2008, 343,73.
8. R. Jung *et al.*, *J. Polym. Sci.: Part B: Polym. Phys.* 2008, 46, pp. 1235–1242.
9. N. Grossiord *et al.*, *Chem. Mater.* 2006, 18, 1089.